

Template synthesis of chromium(III), cobalt(II), nickel(II), copper(II) and cadmium(II) complexes with a tetradentate Schiff base, glyoxilidene-bis-2-aminoethylpyridine

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Some new complexes of Cr^{III}, Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Cu^{II} and Cd^{II} have been synthesized with a tetradentate Schiff base, glyoxilidene-bis-2-aminoethylpyridine. An octahedral geometry has been proposed for the Cr^{III} and Ni^{II} complexes and tetrahedral geometry for the rest of the compounds.

The Schiff bases obtained from dicarbonilic compounds are able to coordinate to metallic ions in different ways¹. In this category are included the complexes with the Schiff bases obtained from glyoxal; for example, the complexes with tetradentate Schiff bases of type (ONNO) obtained by condensation of glyoxal and *o*-aminophenol or anthranilic acid and their adducts with basic molecules having nitrogen as donor (pyridine, imidazol, etc.)². The molecular model shows that the ligand coordinates via two N and two O atoms and form square-planar complexes. We showed earlier that, in certain conditions, it is possible to obtain polynuclear coordination compounds with unusual structures and magnetic properties, using the capability of phenoxo groups to act as bridges³.

In the present paper we report the synthesis and characterization of some complexes of Cr^{III}, Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Cu^{II} and Cd^{II} with a new tetradentate Schiff base of the type (NNNN), obtained through the reaction between glyoxal and 2-aminoethylpyridine, in molar ratio 1:2, glyoxilidene-bis-2-aminoethylpyridine (GAEPy).

Results and Discussion

Except the Co^{II}, Cu^{II} and Cd^{II} complexes that are soluble in methanol, the other compounds are insoluble in common organic solvents and in DMF.

IR spectrum of the ligand showed two bands at 1634 and 1595 cm⁻¹, which are due to $\nu_{C=N}$ from the pyridinic ring and $\nu_{C=N}$ from the azomethinic groups⁴. In the complexes 1-5, the first band red-shifted while the second band blue-shifted. Complex 1 revealed one broad band at 1618

cm⁻¹, which is due to the overlapping of the two above mentioned bands. This proves that the ligand coordinates to the metal ions through the nitrogen atoms of the pyridine rings and azomethinic groups.

The stretching vibrations ν_{OH} from lattice water in the Cr^{III}, Co^{II} and Ni^{II} complexes were found at 3387 (1), 3419 (2) and 3400 cm⁻¹ (3)⁵. The absence of additional bands due to rocking or wagging rules out the possibility of coordination toward central metal ion.

The electronic spectrum of the ligand showed two bands at 29000 and 25000 cm⁻¹, assigned to $n \rightarrow \pi^*$ transitions. Complex 1 showed a shoulder at 15500 cm⁻¹ and band maxima at 16100, 23800 and 32300 cm⁻¹, assigned respectively to ${}^4A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^2T_{2g}$, ${}^4A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}$, ${}^4A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(F)$ and ${}^4A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(P)$ transitions. The shape of the spectrum suggests an octahedral geometry for Cr^{III}. Also, this spectrum presents two bands at 29400 and 25650 cm⁻¹, assigned to $n \rightarrow \pi^*$ transitions. The magnetic moment of complex 2 is 3.95 B.M. Complex 2 showed bands at 15500, 26300 and 30300 cm⁻¹. The former band is assigned to ${}^4A_2 \rightarrow {}^4T_1(P)$ transition, suggesting a tetrahedral geometry for the Co^{II} ion. The other two bands are due to $n \rightarrow \pi^*$ transitions. The magnetic moment value for this complex is 4.57 B.M.

Complex 3 showed bands at 10600, 13500, 16100, 19200, 25000, 25650 and 30770 cm⁻¹. The first five bands are assigned to ${}^3B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^3E_g^a$, ${}^3B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^3B_{2g}$, ${}^3B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^3A_{2g}^a$, ${}^3B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^3E_g^b$ and ${}^3B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^3E_g^c$ transitions, and the other two are due to $n \rightarrow \pi^*$ transitions. The splitting of the bands due to $d-d$ transitions shows that Ni^{II} in this compound has D_{4h} symmetry. In this case the typical value of the magnetic moment (1.9

B.M.) can be explained considering a low-spin \rightleftharpoons high-spin equilibrium⁶.

The shape of the spectrum and position of the bands support tetrahedral geometry for the Cu^{II} complex⁷. Five bands were observed at 10300, 17000, 20800, 26650 and 29850 cm⁻¹. The first three bands may be assigned to ²B₁ → ²B₃, ²B₁ → ²A, ²B₁ → ²A transitions and the last two to *n* → π* transitions. The magnetic moment value for complex **4** is 2.08 B.M. A further confirmation of the tetrahedral geometry for the Cu^{II} complex is revealed by the EPR spectrum. It consists in an isotropic line, with factor *g* = 2.11 and the linewidth of 12.5 mT, specific for a tetrahedral Cu^{II} ion. Complex **5** showed two bands at 26300 and 30300 cm⁻¹, suggesting coordination of the ligand to the metal ion.

Crystal field parameters were calculated⁸ for complex **1** : 10*Dq* = 16100 cm⁻¹ and *B* = 520 cm⁻¹. Taking into account β = *B*/*B*₀ and *B*₀ = 918 cm⁻¹ for the gaseous Cr^{III} ion, we obtained β = 0.56. This relative low value indicates a significant degree of covalency of metal-ligand bonds. The spectrum of the Ni^{II} complex showed characteristic splitting of a distorted octahedral geometry. This fact proves that the compound is tetragonal of type MX₄Y₂.

Molar conductance values measured of the Co^{II}, Cu^{II} and Cd^{II} complexes (164–195 Ω⁻¹ cm² mol⁻¹) show that they are 1 : 2 electrolytes.

The TG and DTG curves for complex **3** showed a mass-loss at 75–120° due to the elimination of the lattice water molecule, experimental value Δ*m*(%) = 4.11 while the calculated value is 4.35%. In the case of complexes **1** and **2**, the experimental mass-loss at 80–150° Δ*m* = 7.81% (calcd. 7.45%) for **1**, and Δ*m* = 8.64% (calcd. 8.33%) for **2**. This indicates elimination of the two lattice water molecules of the complexes.

The structure of complex **4** is as follows :

Experimental

All reagents, metal salts and organic solvents used were of A.R. grade.

Synthesis of the ligand : To a methanolic solution (10 ml) of glyoxal (1 mmol) was added a methanolic solution (10 ml) of 2-aminoethylpyridine (2 mmol). The mixture was stirred for 1 h and then ether was added. The resulting brown solid was washed with ether and dried in a desiccator over H₂SO₄ (98%) : GAEPy, m.p. >250° (Found : C, 71.77; H, 6.54; N, 21.32. Calcd for : C, 72.18; H, 6.76; N, 21.05%); *v*_{max} (KBr) 2928, 1634, 1595, 1568, 1543,

1477, 1438, 1384, 1125, 1052, 1003, 766, 704, 619, 510 cm⁻¹.

Synthesis of the complex : To a methanolic solution (10 ml) of glyoxal (1 mmol), was added a methanolic solution (10 ml) of 2-aminoethylpyridine (2 mmol). The mixture was stirred for 15 min, then added the methanolic solution (10 ml) of the transition metal salts (1 mmol) [MX₃, where M = Cr^{III} and X = Cl, or MX₂, where M = Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Cu^{II}, Cd^{II} and X = Cl]. The solution was refluxed for 6 h, then concentrated to half of its volume, ether added and the resulting solid was washed with ether and dried in a desiccator over H₂SO₄ (98%) : [Cr(GAEPy)Cl₂].2H₂O (**1**), green powder, m.p. >250° (Found : C, 41.85; H, 4.57; N, 11.83; Cr, 11.02. Calcd. for : C, 41.69; H, 4.77; N, 12.16; Cr, 11.29%), *v*_{max} (KBr) 3387, 1618, 1571, 1470, 1443, 1368, 1250, 1158, 1050, 934, 770, 666, 523 cm⁻¹; [Co(GAEPy)Cl₂].2H₂O (**2**), blue powder, m.p. >250° (Found : C, 44.12; H, 4.94; N, 12.67; Co, 13.21. Calcd. for : C, 44.44; H, 5.09; N, 12.96; Co, 13.65%), *v*_{max} (KBr) 3419, 3078, 2967, 2934, 1631, 1605, 1565, 1483, 1441, 1378, 1315, 1245, 1157, 1087, 1021, 782, 768, 668, 645, 584, 460, 423 cm⁻¹; [Ni(GAEPy)Cl₂].H₂O (**3**), green powder, m.p. >250° (Found : C, 46.23; H, 4.67; N, 13.85; Ni, 13.72. Calcd. for : C, 46.41; H, 4.83; N, 13.53; Ni, 14.18%), *v*_{max} (KBr) 3400, 1650, 1601, 1567, 1542, 1480, 1440, 1386, 1313, 1262, 1155, 1109, 1062, 1017, 1001, 951, 763, 700, 638, 511, 426 cm⁻¹; [Cu(GAEPy)Cl₂] (**4**), green powder, m.p. >250° (Found : C, 47.63; H, 4.21; N, 13.65; Cu, 15.37. Calcd. for : C, 47.94; H, 4.49; N, 13.98; Cu, 15.85%), *v*_{max} (KBr) 1653, 1603, 1568, 1480, 1358, 1314, 1252, 1156, 1107, 1055, 1027, 1002, 768, 695, 511, 429 cm⁻¹; [Cd(GAEPy)Cl₂] (**5**), white powder, m.p. >250° (Found : C, 42.28; H, 3.84; N, 11.96; Cd, 24.77. Calcd. for : C, 42.72; H, 4.00; N, 12.46; Cd, 25.01%), *v*_{max} (KBr) 3064, 3018, 2969, 2927, 1642, 1595, 1567, 1548, 1478, 1436, 1372, 1315, 1248, 1226, 1154, 1103, 1083, 1055, 1005, 950, 813, 766, 686, 668, 635, 585, 506, 468, 406 cm⁻¹.

Elemental analysis data were obtained with a Carlo-Erba 1104 analyzer. The metal contents were determined using standard procedures⁹. IR spectra (KBr) were measured on a BIO-RAD FTS 135 spectrophotometer and electronic spectra on a Carl-Zeiss VSU-2P spectrophotometer (diffuse reflectance technique) with MgO as a standard. EPR spectra were measured at room temperature by a X-band spectrometer employing 100 kHz modulation of the magnetic field and operating at 9060 MHz and using Mn^{II} as standard. Paramagnetic susceptibility was determined at room temperature (298 K) by Faraday method using Hg[Co(NCS)₄] as a standard. TG and DTG curves were recorded with a heat rate of 10 K/min using a Du Pont 2000 instrument. Conductance (10⁻³ M solutions in methanol) was measured using a OK 102 conductometer.

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